

Deliverable 2.1

Concept and methodology for collecting volumes of biogenic feedstock

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for collecting volumes of
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Index of Contents

1	Introduction.....	8
2	Definitions and description of feedstock.....	10
2.1	Grown Feedstock.....	11
2.1.1	Agricultural feedstocks.....	11
2.1.2	Forestry feedstocks.....	12
2.1.3	Aquatic feedstocks.....	12
2.2	Residues.....	13
2.2.1	Residues from agriculture.....	13
2.2.2	Residues from forestry.....	13
2.2.3	Residues from the processing industry.....	13
2.3	Waste.....	14
3	Methodology and data collection.....	15
3.1	Identification of biological feedstocks and relevant data sources.....	15
3.1.1	Type of feedstock.....	15
3.1.2	Applicability of bio-based feedstock for material use.....	15
3.1.3	Global production and European volume of bio-based feedstocks.....	18
3.1.4	Imports and Exports of bio-based feedstock into the EU.....	19
3.2	Analysis of identified feedstocks.....	19
3.2.1	Agricultural feedstocks.....	20
3.2.2	Forestry feedstocks.....	21
3.2.3	Aquaculture feedstocks.....	21
3.2.4	Residues.....	23
3.2.4.1	Residues from Agriculture.....	23
3.2.4.2	Residues from forestry.....	23
3.2.5	<i>Residues from the processing industry</i>	24
3.2.5.1	Residues from food processing.....	24
3.2.5.2	Residues from other processing industries.....	25
3.2.6	Wastes.....	25
3.3	Trade.....	25
3.4	Biogenic Feedstocks in Material Use.....	28
4	Preliminary Results.....	29
5	Conclusions.....	31
6	References.....	32

Index of Tables

Table 1: Potential ways to classify biobased feedstocks (Taken from: Lewandowski (2018)).....	10
Table 2: Classification according to the economic sector of production of the most relevant EU bio-based feedstocks for the EU bio-based industry (Taken from: Stratmann et al. (2022)).....	11
Table 3: Organic waste generation in the food industry (Fehrenbach et al. 2019)	24
Table 4: Overview of covered biological feedstocks and their respective HS codes	26
Table 5: Preliminary results of trade flow analysis	30

Index of Figures

Figure 1: Industrial Material use of Biomass in Europe in 2015 (nova-Institut GmbH 2015)	16
Figure 2: Bio- and CO ₂ -based Economy: Feedstocks, Processes and Products (nova-Institut GmbH 2023).....	17
Figure 3: Pathways to bio-based polymers (nova-Institut GmbH 2022)	18
Figure 4: FAOSTAT:: Example for a query to the database (FAOSTAT 2023c)	21
Figure 5: Example for a query to the database FishStat (FAOSTAT 2023a)	22
Figure 6: Eurostat: Example for a query to the database (screenshot; source: ...).....	28

Partners short names

TUB	Technische Universität Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	nova-Institut für Politische und Ökologische Innovation GmbH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Abbreviations

EU	European Union
WP	Work package
B2B	Business-to-business
SCS	Sustainable Certification Schemes
JRC	Joint Research Centre
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
STAR4BBS	Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
MDF	Medium-density fibreboard
OSB	Oriented Strand Board

Executive Summary

This report is an important part of the Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems (STAR4BBS) project. The main objective of the STAR4BBS project is to harness the potential of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and labels to facilitate a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. This includes the development of indicators and an innovative monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, as well as business-to-business (B2B) labels and traceability schemes relevant for biological feedstocks, bio-based materials and products.

In order to establish a competent monitoring system for the verification of bio-based SCS and labels, an important preliminary step is the collection and systematic review of information related to international and EU SCS, B2B labels and their relevance for biological feedstocks, bio-based materials and products. At the core of this effort is the identification and verification of relevant and the derived bio-based intermediates, materials and products within the European bioeconomy. To accomplish this, the objective of the Work Package 2 of the STAR4BBS project is to gather precise global trade data and information regarding the volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based materials imported into the EU in order to identify the most relevant biomass flows. The aim is to provide a comprehensive overview of certified and non-certified biomass flows and thus contribute significantly to the assessment of the impact and contribution of sustainability certification and labelling.

In this context, the main focus of this report is to outline a conceptual framework and methodology to identify and analyse the production and trade volumes of bio-based feedstocks. The analysis relies heavily on a comprehensive assessment of existing and consolidated market databases such as JRC, UNCTAD, FAO and EUROSTAT, coupled with information from existing literature, results from other projects and the collective expertise within the project consortium.

The approach and methodology developed to collect volumes of biogenic feedstocks shows that a standardised approach to quantifying production and trade figures in this field is not possible. Due to the specific nature of the feedstock and the associated economic sector, different databases have to be consulted to access relevant data and information. For example, while the FAOSTAT database mainly covers primary biomass and feedstocks, the PRODCOM database is more useful for secondary feedstocks. Importantly, several other feedstocks, in particular agricultural, forestry and manufacturing residues, are not covered by these conventional databases. In these cases, the quantification is based on a number of plausible assumptions, often relying on alternative data sources such as literature or results from other studies. The harmonisation of data from different databases and the incorporation of reasonable assumptions are crucial to the design of the methodology. This harmonised combination of data and reasonable assumptions plays a key role in constructing a robust framework for assessing the quantities of different biogenic feedstocks, effectively recognising the complex diversity within the bioeconomy landscape.

1 Introduction

The bio-based industry plays a crucial role in the transition to a more sustainable and circular economy. It spans several sectors, including agriculture, forestry, chemicals, plastics and textiles (Porc et al. 2022). The industry is characterised by the use of biological feedstocks, such as crops, wood and waste streams, to produce a wide range of materials and products. As a result, it has the potential to make a significant contribution to sustainability goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving resource efficiency and promoting the circular economy. It can also have a positive impact on socio-economic objectives such as local development through the use of regional resources and the creation of green jobs.

However, the use of bio-based feedstocks needs to be carefully regulated and controlled to mitigate negative environmental and social impacts, such as deforestation, soil erosion, biodiversity loss and the exploitation of child labour in developing countries (Bauchmüller et al. (2021); (Weiss et al. 2012)).

To facilitate this transition and ensure the credibility of sustainability claims, Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels serve as critical tools. They provide independent verification and validation of sustainability efforts and promote transparency and accountability throughout supply chains. However, these SCS face challenges such as limited scope, high costs and lack of harmonisation, being the last one, the main drawback (Mori Junior et al. 2016).

Currently, there is a large number of SCS and labels in European Union, each with their own set of criteria and standards. This large number can lead to confusion among businesses and consumers, as well as increased operational costs for companies operating in several countries and seeking regional or national certifications (Mori Junior et al. 2016). Businesses are often burdened with providing documentation to demonstrate compliance with different criteria. For consumers, the plethora of labels with different criteria and standards makes it difficult to make informed choices.

The STAR4BBS project aims at overcoming these problems and maximise the potential of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. The STAR4BBS project focuses on developing indicators and a new monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes, B2B labels and related traceability systems for organic raw materials and bio-based materials and products. This information will provide the basis for much needed harmonisation between SCS that will lead to an increased transparency of global and EU trade flows.

At the beginning of the project, we started collecting and systematically evaluating data on trade flows. This serves as the basis for the project's analysis and strategic approach to gain an accurate insight into the current state of the European bioeconomy. In this context, within Work Package 2 some of the tasks will include the collection of specific data and information on the volume of biological raw materials and bio-based materials and products within global trade flows, and the distinction between certified and non-certified biomass flows. The focus will be on imports into and exports from the EU, taking into account geographical distribution. The aim is to improve the understanding of existing biomass movements within the European bioeconomy. Furthermore, the potential impacts of certification schemes on sustainability goals will be highlighted, including the differences between SCS.

This deliverable presents the concept and methodology used for identifying and quantifying production and trade volumes of bio-based feedstocks and is intended to serve as a basis for the evaluation of biomass trade flows. The analysis is mainly based on the review of existing and consolidated market databases such as GFS, UNCTAD, FAO and EUROSTAT databases, as well as on the use of the existing knowledge of the project consortium.

At the beginning of this report, the feedstocks relevant to the EU bio-based industry are described and classified according to their type and the economic sector to which they belong. These categories include primary biomass (e.g., starch, sugar and lignocellulosic feedstocks) and secondary biomass (e.g., organic waste) (Chapter 0). Chapter 3 describes the methodology used and describes how biogenic feedstocks that relevant to the European bioeconomy are identified. Based on this, we describe different methodological approaches for quantifying production and trade figures for each feedstock group. First quantification results of the trade flow analysis are shown in Chapter 4. The full analysis of trade flows and its results will be presented in the Deliverable 2.4 - "Report on volumes of biogenic raw materials and bio-based products and materials" due in project month 24. Finally, in the last section we draw a brief conclusion.

The relevance of this work is derived from its future use within the STAR4BBS project. In particular, in WP2, the developed concept will support the ongoing analysis of trade flows. At the same time, it will form the basis for the assessment aimed at distinguishing between certified and non-certified flows and the impact of certification and labelling schemes on market access and trade of biological feedstocks for industrial purposes and bio-based materials and products (Task 2.2). Furthermore, building on selected bio-based feedstocks described and identified in this report (Chapter 4), potential test cases in representative bio-based value chain have been identified and selected, to be used for conducting further project analysis. " In particular, these test cases will be then analysed in WP5 from the perspective of costs and benefits.

The term **biomass** can be defined as plant or animal material, including substances produced from and by microorganisms, as well as derived organic molecules (Lewandowski 2018). Sometimes the concept of biomass and bio-based resources are used interchangeably. However, strictly speaking, the term of **bio-based resources** is broader than that of biomass, as it includes all resources containing non-fossil, organic carbon of recent origin, usually less than 100 years old and derived from living plants, animals, algae, microorganisms or organic waste streams (Lewandowski 2018). The term biomass is most commonly used in the context of energy production and the discussion between the use of edible and non-edible biomass (i.e., food-vs-fuel debate).

The term **feedstock** refers to biomass or bio-based resources from the perspective of industrial processes. For example, corn stover is, generally speaking, a bio-based resource. However, the term “biomass” is used for the bioenergy industry, while the term “feedstock” is mostly used for the materials and chemicals industry.

Feedstocks used in the bioeconomy are highly diverse and come from very different sources, constituting the starting point of bio-based value chains. Feedstock can be classified in multiple ways (Table 1). For instance, according to the organisms where the feedstock comes from, i.e., animals, plants, microorganisms, etc.; according to the sector from which the biomass is sourced from (agriculture, forestry, fishery and aquaculture, algae and microorganisms, waste); according to their origin (feedstock derived from animals, plants, microorganisms, etc.) and/or according to their major biomass component (sugar, starch, vegetable oil, etc.), although the last classification is mostly used in the context of feedstock from the agriculture feedstock (Lewandowski, 2018). In addition, biomass or feedstock can be classified according to the economic sector of origin (i.e., primary sector, secondary sector and tertiary sector) (Table 2). This classification should not be confused with the classification used in the context of “food-vs-fuel” debate, namely first, second and third generation feedstock.

Table 1: Potential ways to classify biobased feedstocks (Taken from: Lewandowski (2018))

Organisms which produce biomass	Sector of biomass production	Major biomass components (molecular formula)
Plants	Agriculture	Sugars (e.g. glucose, $C_6H_{12}O_6$)
Animals	Forestry	Starch ($C_6H_{10}O_5$) _n
Microorganisms	Fishery and aquaculture	Cellulose ($C_6H_{10}O_5$) _n
	Algae and microorganisms	Hemicelluloses (e.g. xylose, $C_5H_{10}O_5$)
	Waste	Lignin (coumaryl alcohol, $C_9H_{10}O_2$; coniferyl alcohol, $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$; sinapyl alcohol, $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$)
		Oils (triglycerides, e.g. oleic acid, $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$)
		Proteins (amino acids, e.g. alanine, $C_3H_7NO_2$)

Table 2: Classification according to the economic sector of production of the most relevant EU bio-based feedstocks for the EU bio-based industry (Taken from: Stratmann et al. (2022))

Sector	Origin	Grown feedstock and its residues	Waste
Primary sector	Agriculture and horticulture	Sugar: sugar beet Starch: Wheat, maize, barley, oat, potato Oil: Rape, sunflower, olives Fibres: Flax, hemp Miscellaneous: Miscanthus Residues from agriculture and horticulture, Food loss in the field	
	Forestry	Spruce, beech, silver birch, ash, scots pine, oak, douglas fir, sycamore, short rotation crops, plant resins, cork Residues from forestry	
	Aquatic feedstock (fisheries, aquaculture, algae)	Micro- and macroalgae Residues from fisheries (e.g., by-catch) Residues from aquaculture Algae leftovers	
Secondary sector	Processing, food industry, textile industry	Residues from forest-based industries (e.g., woodworking facilities, construction), pulp & paper Residues from sugar, starch or oilseeds processing Residues from fermentation processes Residues from meat, poultry and fish processing industries (fat, bones, skin, etc.) (Depending on value) Biogenic gases generated from industrial processes or bioenergy plants	Industrial wastewater and sludge, Recycled paper Animal manure
		Leftovers, textile residues	Textile waste (separately collected in clothing bin)
Tertiary sector, Municipalities, Households	Wholesale and retail, restaurants, hotels, catering		Bio-waste (incl. consumer food waste), sewage sludge and waste water from municipalities, textile waste (not separately collected)

The following sections present the feedstocks relevant to the EU bioeconomy, differentiated by their economic value and production dependency. This distinction covers grown feedstocks, residues and wastes.

2.1 Grown Feedstock

Grown biomass refers to raw materials that are either naturally or intentionally cultivated by humans and can be used profitably in the bio-based value chain. It includes products from agriculture, horticulture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture.

2.1.1 Agricultural feedstocks

Agricultural feedstocks relevant to the bio-based industries refer to organic materials grown and harvested by agricultural activities for use as raw materials in various industries. These feedstocks can include crops that can be broadly classified according to their main content as sugar crops, starch crops, vegetable oil crops and fibre crops (cellulose is the main component).

- Sugar crops: Crops that contain large amounts of sucrose. Of these, the most common are sugar cane (*Saccharum officinarum*) and sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*). Sugar cane is a perennial grass cultivated mainly in the tropics whereas sugar beet is an annual crop used for sugar production in cooler climates. Both sugar beets and sugar cane have high water contents, accounting for about 75% of the total weight of the plants. The sugar content of sugar cane ranges from 10 to 15% of the total weight, while that of sugar beets is between 13 and 18%.
- Starch Crops: Crops containing starch (long chains of sugar molecules) that can be degraded to glucose molecules, which can then be used as a fermentation substrate. From the feedstock perspective, most common starch crops worldwide are wheat, corn, barley, rye,

millet and sorghum, potatoes, cassava and sweet potatoes. Since the starch can be found in the seeds of the plants or the root/shoot, the fibrous part can be used as a residue and become feedstock for another processes, such as the production of bioenergy or treated for feed. Despite containing high amounts of starch, from a feedstock perspective, rice is not considered a starch crop, but a grain (ETIP Bioenergy 2023).

- Vegetable oil crops: Refer to crops with high oil content from which oil is derived from the extraction of triglycerols from the seeds or nuts. Aside from its food applications, vegetable oil can be used in oleochemistry for the production of polymers, surfactants, lubricants, and coating/colours. The most commonly used vegetables for industrial purposes are the kernel palm oil plant, rapeseed, coconut, sunflower, linseed, and castor oil. The most commonly grown vegetable oil crops are rapeseed, sunflower and soybean (Sarmiento 2016)
- Fibre Crops: Crops that produce fibre as raw material for multiple applications. Fibre can come from the seeds (e.g., cotton), the bast (e.g., flax, hemp) and the leaves (e.g., yucca). Other sources include grass fibre, palm fibre and woody fibre. Fibre crops are commonly used for clothing products, but they also have application in the pulp and paper industries, in packaging and in building and construction.

2.1.2 Forestry feedstocks

Forestry feedstock encompasses all the woody biomass and the complex molecules that make wood, such as cellulose and lignin. Forestry feedstock include tree logs, cork, wood from forest management practices (roundwood) and another woody biomass. Forestry feedstock can be further classified into hardwood and softwood. The main difference resides in the presence of resin canals, being absent in hardwood species and present in the majority of softwood species. The internal structure determines its use, for example, hardwood is preferred for energy use, construction, furniture and other products. Common hardwood species include oak, ash and beech. Typical softwood trees include Douglas fir, pine and redwood, commonly used for pulp and paper, although these species can also be used for construction and cheap furniture.

2.1.3 Aquatic feedstocks

Aquaculture feedstock refers to organic material grown and harvested from aquaculture activities, including various aquatic organisms such as fish, shellfish, algae and aquatic plants. Fishery feedstocks include by-catch from fishing practices that is not suitable either for human consumption or further downstream processing.

Microalgae is a group of photosynthetic unicellular organisms able to grow in sea, fresh and ground water (Lewandowski 2018). As feedstock, microalgae are capable of producing large quantities of biochemical components, including lipids, carbohydrates, proteins and other high-value added molecules such as carotenoids, phytosterols, and antifungal, antiviral and antimicrobial components (Lewandowski 2018).

Macroalgae or seaweeds are a diverse group of multicellular plant-like organisms that grow in aquatic environments. Their most common, and oldest use, is for food and feed (Rahikainen et al. 2021). However, they are also considered as good sources of biopolymers and other chemicals and are suitable for biofuel production (Da Rosa et al. 2023). For food and feed use, if not used immediately macroalgae have to go through a mild processing, such as drying and milling, due to their poor preservation capacities (Rahikainen et al. 2021). Then it can be rehydrated previous to its consumption or can be used as a flour to add nutrients, minerals or flavour to foodstuffs or feed (Rahikainen et al. 2021). Like microalgae, macroalgae research is an active field. Recent innovations in the materials and product sector include the utilization of seaweeds for packaging, straws and bioplastics (Rahikainen et al. 2021). In addition, macroalgae are used for polymers (polysaccharides)

such as hydrocolloids, alginates and carrageenan commonly used in the food and biotechnology sectors (Rahikainen et al. 2021).

2.2 Residues

Residues are leftover materials, by-products or substances that remain after a process, activity or operation has taken place. They are usually not the primary intended outcome of the process and may have potential for further use or reuse in various applications.

In RED II, Art. 2, a distinction is made between two types of residues (European Parliament and Council 2018):

- 1) Agricultural, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry residues: Residues that are directly generated by agriculture, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry and that do not include residues from related industries or processing.
- 2) (Process) residue: Substance that is not the end product(s) that a production process directly seeks to produce; it is not a primary aim of the production process and the process has not been deliberately modified to produce it.

2.2.1 Residues from agriculture

Agricultural residues consist of husks and shells, straws, stems, seeds and roots, bagasse, pomace and hulls that result from the processing of agricultural feedstocks.

Husks and shells from rice and nuts have high calorific content, which makes them ideal for bioenergy production. Straws, stalks and stems are the predominant leftover of cereal crops such as wheat (wheat straw), corn (corn stover) and barely (barley straw) are rich in bioactive compounds which makes them suitable for animal feed or for cellulose-based materials such as paper, textiles and biodegradable plastics. Bagasse is the fibrous leftover from the extraction of sugar cane juice. Due to its high cellulose content, it can be used for paper and packaging. Pomace is the term used to describe fruit peels, pulp and seeds after fruit processing, the resulting mix is rich in bioactive compounds such as antioxidants and can be processed into dietary supplements, cosmetics or other functional foods. It can also be used as feed for livestock.

Residues from agriculture can also be used as fertilisers and animal bedding.

2.2.2 Residues from forestry

Forestry residues are the by products from forest harvesting and it is a mix of leaves, branches, and pieces of trunk which are the remains of plantation thinning, logging and natural attrition. The most common use of forestry residues is for bioenergy production, but it is also recognised as a common source for local heating and cooking. For alternative uses, forestry residues can be milled and grinded to obtain sawdust (See 2.2.3 Residues from the processing industry). It is worth noting that in the EU not all forestry residues are available, since some of it must remain in situ for the provision of ecological benefits.

2.2.3 Residues from the processing industry

In addition to residues from the primary sectors, the processing sectors also produce residues. The food industry is an important source of biogenic raw materials. Feedstocks from the food industry include organic materials and by-products generated during food processing and production. These feedstocks include a range of materials such as animal fats from slaughterhouses and meat

processing plants, fish meal and oil from fish processing, sugar beet pulp from sugar production, spent malt from breweries, used cooking oil and other residues not suitable for human consumption. However, they can be used in the production of value-added bio-based products.

Other types of manufacturing residues include glycerol, a by-product of biodiesel and soap production. Glycerol is used in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and as a feedstock for chemical production. Tall oil, another feedstock, is a valuable by-product of the pulp and paper sector. It is produced during the kraft pulping process, which is used to separate cellulose fibers from wood for paper and related pulp-based products.

Residues from the wood industry also include residues from sawn wood and sawmill activities (e.g., sawdust). These residues can be used for the production of wood-based products. Wood-based products are mainly chipboard, MDF (medium density fiberboard), OSB (oriented strand board), wood fiber insulation and wood-plastic composites (Sarmiento 2016).

2.3 Waste

Waste feedstock are streams of material that have no or negative economic value. However, the definition of what is waste or what is not waste is not clear (Stratmann et al. 2022). In some cases, what is considered waste for an industrial sector can be a valuable source of material or molecules for another one. In the context of this study, waste is classified in municipal waste (namely the organic fraction of municipal solid waste), sludge and waste water.

The organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) consists of organic materials found in municipal solid waste, such as food waste, garden waste and other organic household waste. These can be used as raw materials for various applications. OFMSW can be processed to obtain a sludge from solid fraction and waste water, the liquid fraction of waste.

It is estimated that in the European Union, 35% of the municipal waste is of organic bio-waste as it also contains residues from agriculture and industry sectors and around 30% of its solid fraction is organic (Ioannidou et al. 2020). The composition of OFMSW varies widely across regions and depends on the number of inhabitants, the socioeconomic condition and habits of the population. Composition is also seasonal as consumption patterns and generated waste (i.e., from gardening) change (Campuzano and González-Martínez 2016).

The most common use of OFMSW is as feedstock for the production of biogas and its subsequent upgrading to biomethane. Alternative pathways include OFMSW as feedstock for the production of bio-based chemicals via fermentation in biorefineries, including ethanol, lactic acid, succinic acid, biosurfactants polyols and polyurethanes (Ioannidou et al. 2020).

Sludge, the residual semi-solid material produced during wastewater treatment is rich in organic matter, nutrients and trace elements. Sludge can be processed to extract oils, fats and lipids. Alternatively, it can be used as feedstock for biogas production or soil fertilizer. Similar to sludge, wastewater is rich in nutrients and trace elements that can be extracted and used in fertilizers. Depending on the source of the wastewater, this can be reused for rural or urban irrigation.

3 Methodology and data collection

In the following section, we describe the methodology developed to collect and analyse data on the volumes of primary and secondary biological feedstocks in global trade flows to the EU using a long list of databases (e.g., FAO, UN, Eurostat, etc.). Potential data gaps will be filled by additional data sources from the literature, results of other research projects and expert interviews.

3.1 Identification of biological feedstocks and relevant data sources

In order to quantify and identify the relevant feedstocks for the European bioeconomy and their potential data sources, the following criteria have been established:

- Type of feedstock
- Applicability of bio-based feedstock for material use
- Global production and European volume of bio-based feedstocks
- Imports and Exports of bio-based feedstock into the EU

3.1.1 Type of feedstock

The feedstocks used in the EU bioeconomy are very diverse and come from very different sources. For practical reasons, the relevant feedstocks for the EU bio-based industry have been classified according to the economic sector to which they belong (primary, secondary, tertiary) (as described in chapter 0). Table 2 provides an overview of the feedstocks as a basis for the analysis (Stratmann et al. 2022).

3.1.2 Applicability of bio-based feedstock for material use

The industrial sectors of interest for this study are those relevant to the decarbonisation of the EU economy and included in the Bioeconomy Strategy of the European Commission (2018).

These sectors are:

- Chemicals, paints and coatings
- Construction
- Cosmetics, home care, hygiene products
- Electronics
- Furniture
- Packaging
- Plastics
- Pulp and paper
- Textiles

The scope of the STAR4BBS project excludes the food & feed and bioenergy sectors. Therefore, the next step is to determine whether the defined and listed feedstocks used in the bio-based industrial sectors are relevant to the project scope. Based on literature and desktop research, an attempt was made to identify value chains using bio-based feedstocks in these industrial sectors. There is a variety of value chains based on bio-based feedstocks and a large number of different feedstocks, processes, intermediate and final products as well as industrial sectors that can be identified in bio-based supply chains (Figure 1 & Figure 2). In addition, value chains show diversity even within individual industrial sectors (Figure 3). Using this information, feedstocks that are currently used exclusively in the bioenergy or food and feed sectors can be specifically excluded from the analysis.

Figure 1: Industrial Material use of Biomass in Europe in 2015 (nova-Institut GmbH 2015)

Figure 2: Bio- and CO₂-based Economy: Feedstocks, Processes and Products (nova-Institut GmbH 2023)

Figure 3: Pathways to bio-based polymers (nova-Institut GmbH 2022)

3.1.3 Global production and European volume of bio-based feedstocks

Depending on the type of feedstock, data and information from recognised and freely available databases are used to quantify the global and European production of bio-based feedstocks. For the quantification of primary biomass and feedstocks, the FAOSTAT database is used (FAOSTAT 2023c). FAOSTAT is a comprehensive database of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). It provides access to global and European statistics and information on agricultural production, trade, resource use and food security, and is a valuable resource for decision-makers, researchers and organisations. Among other things, the FAOSTAT database provides information on the production and area of agricultural crops and their processed products for different countries and regions. In addition to agricultural crops, FAOSTAT also provides information on forestry production volumes. In general, FAOSTAT data are used in a number of studies. For example, in studies examining global and European biomass supply and demand

(Piotrowski et al. 2015), assessing food security (FAO et al. 2023) or investigating climate change (Tubiello et al. 2013).

Potential production figures for residual biomass from the processing industry can also be obtained from the PRODCOM database. PRODCOM stands for "PRODUCTION COMunautaire" and is a classification for the production of goods in the EU. It is used to present information on the production and trade of products in different industrial sectors. In the PRODCOM database, products are classified according to the NACE classification (Nomenclature statistique des arces exonimiques dans le Cimmunautaire européen - Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community) by assigning them a code and grouping them in classes according to their use (Eurostat 2008).

For the information and data on the production of biological feedstocks that are not included in the above-mentioned databases, data gaps had to be filled by additional data sources from the literature, results from other research projects and expert interviews. The procedures for this step are explained in more detail in chapter 3.2.

3.1.4 Imports and Exports of bio-based feedstock into the EU

As mentioned before, one of the main objectives of the STAR4BBS project is to collect specific data and information on the volumes of certified and non-certified biological feedstocks in global trade flows, with a focus on imports to (and exports from) the EU and their geographical distribution. To achieve this goal, the United Nations (UN) international trade database Comtrade will be used as the main source for determining trade figures of biological raw materials to and from the EU (UN Comtrade 2023). It is a comprehensive source of trade data and statistics from around the world, collecting detailed information on trade between countries. One of the most important elements of the Comtrade database is the trade codes used to classify traded goods. The two main classification systems used in Comtrade are the SITC (Standard International Trade Classification) codes and the HS (Harmonised System) codes. The SITC codes consist of four digits and provide a more general classification of goods. An HS code, on the other hand, consists of six to ten digits and provides a detailed and precise categorisation of goods and is currently the most widely used classification system for international trade in the world. The first six digits of the HS code are globally unique and are used by almost all countries for customs purposes. The additional digits can be used by individual countries to create specific classifications for certain groups of goods.

In addition to the Comtrade database, trade information can also be obtained from the PRODCOM database. As in the case of production volumes, gaps in the data have to be filled by well-founded assumptions based on market studies and literature.

3.2 Analysis of identified feedstocks

The quantification and analysis of biomass feedstocks is done according to the type of biomass, its origin and, as described in the previous section, on the basis of the presented databases and their data quality.

3.2.1 Agricultural feedstocks

World and European production figures for biological feedstocks are extracted from the FAOSTAT database and require a specific query to obtain the requested data:

1. Access the FAOSTAT database.

To access the data and information, you must first access the "Crops and animal products" database on the FAOSTAT website (FAOSTAT 2023b).

2. Selection of data category

The next step is to select the data category. It is possible to obtain information on the cultivation and production capacity of an entire crop (category "Crops, primary") or on the products (feedstock) already processed from the crop (category "Crops processed").

3. Selection of crop or the processed feedstock

Within the data categories it is possible to search for and select data on whole crops (e.g., sunflower seeds) or information on the production of feedstocks already processed from these crops (e.g., sunflower oil).

4. Filtering data by production

Once the biological raw material has been chosen, the key figure "Production quantity" is selected. This is the indicator that shows the produced quantity of the feedstock.

5. Filter data by geographical region

In order to obtain global and/or European production figures, it is necessary to filter the data by geographical region. The "Area" parameter makes it possible to filter the production figures by "World" or by "EU-27".

6. Filtering data by period

In order to obtain the most recent data, the "Years" parameter allows you to select the desired period or year. In our analysis we used the most recent year available.

Finally, the database allows you to extract the collected data and download it in various formats, such as tables, and insert it into your own datasheet. The Figure 4 shows a screenshot of a possible query to the FAOSTAT database.

The screenshot shows the FAOSTAT website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Data', 'Selected Indicators', 'Compare Data', 'Definitions and Standards', and 'FAQ'. A search bar is on the right. Below the navigation is a main header 'Crops and livestock products' with a 'Back to domains' button. The main content area is divided into several sections: 'COUNTRIES', 'REGIONS', 'SPECIAL GROUPS', 'ELEMENTS', 'ITEMS', 'ITEMS AGGREGATED', and 'YEARS'. Each section has a search bar and a list of options. The 'SPECIAL GROUPS' section has 'European Union (27) + (Total)' selected. The 'ELEMENTS' section has 'Production Quantity' selected. The 'ITEMS' section has 'Sunflower-seed oil, crude' selected. The 'YEARS' section has '2021' selected. At the bottom, there are options for 'Output Type' (Table, Pivot), 'File Type' (CSV, XLS), 'Thousand Separator in 'Show Data'' (None, Comma, Period), and 'Output Formatting Options' (Flags, Notes, Codes). On the right side, there is a sidebar with 'Crops and livestock products' information, 'Bulk Downloads' (All Data, All Data Normalized, All Area Groups, Africa, Americas, Asia, Europe, Oceania), 'Last Update' (March 24, 2023), and 'Related Documents' (Hen Eggs technical conversion factor, Revision of the agriculture production data domain, Methodology - Crops and Livestock, Update history).

Figure 4: FAOSTAT:: Example for a query to the database (FAOSTAT 2023c)

3.2.2 Forestry feedstocks

Wood production figures can also be obtained from the FAOSTAT database by following the steps described above. Information can be obtained by accessing the “Forestry Production and Trade database” on the FAOSTAT website.

3.2.3 Aquaculture feedstocks

Information on production and trade is also available from FAO. FAO provides specific databases for fisheries and aquaculture (FAOSTAT 2023a). These include, for example, information on global algae production (cultivated and wild), but also data on other aquatic organisms, plants, fish, and more, filtered by region (Figure 5).

Fisheries and Aquaculture

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Global aquaculture production Quantity (1950 - 2021)

This database contains aquaculture production statistics by country or territory, species item, FAO Major Fishing Area and culture environment. Global aquaculture production (Quantity)

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- Crustaceans
- Diadromous fishes
- Freshwater fishes
- Marine fishes

Figure 5: Example for a query to the database FishStat (FAOSTAT 2023a)

3.2.4 Residues

3.2.4.1 Residues from Agriculture

Estimates and information on the potential occurrence of residues and by-products of agricultural production, such as straw, cannot be obtained directly from FAOSTAT or other databases. However, numerous studies offer the possibility of estimating the amount of crop residues by making assumptions about the ratios between the primary crop and the residues of specific crops. In agronomy, various measures of this relationship are used: the most prominent are the harvest index, which is the proportion of the primary crop harvest in the total above-ground plant biomass, and the grain/straw ratio. These measures of the relationship are specific to each crop. Based on these measures of the relationship, harvest factors can be calculated, which allow the extrapolation of the total residue biomass from the primary crop harvest as reported in the crop statistics (Eurostat 2018). Using these harvest factors, the total amount of theoretically maximum usable crop residues can be determined. However, most of this total remains on agricultural land. There are strict limits to the removal of by-products from the agricultural system for external use if soil fertility is to be maintained in the sense of sustainable use. Piotrowski et al. (2015) assumed an average of about 25% for the usable fraction of co-products, which we also use for this analysis.

An estimation equation to calculate the usable amount of agricultural residues is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Crop production} \times \text{harvest factor} \times \text{dry matter content} \times 25\% \text{ (used)} \\ & = \text{Available quantity of agricultural residues} \end{aligned}$$

3.2.4.2 Residues from forestry

A similar approach is used to estimate forest residues. Forest residues are a mixture of leaves, bark, stem parts and branches (Rudra and Jayathilake 2022). According to Tripathi et al. (2019), 20% of harvested wood biomass is lost or occurs as residue. FAOSTAT reports the total roundwood production in its "Forestry Production and Trade database", which includes "industrial roundwood" and "wood fuel" in the statistics, but not forest residues. These must be added to the total value.

The following equation can be used to estimate the amount of forest residues:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{Roundwood, total (from FAOSTAT)}) \times 1,2 - \text{Roundwood, total (from FAOSTAT)} \\ & = \text{Available quantity of forestry residues} \end{aligned}$$

3.2.5 Residues from the processing industry

As the feedstocks in this sector come from different processes and sources, and the availability of data in the above-mentioned databases is very uneven or incomplete, it is not possible to apply a uniform quantification methodology, so that the quantification of the production figure can only be achieved on a case-by-case basis, depending on the feedstock considered and the availability of data.

3.2.5.1 Residues from food processing

It can be difficult to find comprehensive data on food processing feedstocks, as not all data is publicly or centrally available. In addition, data can vary from country to country and from processing company to processing company.

Therefore, the only option left here is to estimate the quantities of sectoral waste streams based on the amount of food produced in the different industries and the proportions of by-products generated derived from the literature.

Table 3, based on a study from the German Environment Agency (Fehrenbach et al. 2019), shows the organic waste/residual materials generated by industry and commerce and their quantities.

Table 3: Organic waste generation in the food industry (Fehrenbach et al. 2019)

Industry sector	Substrate	Amount (fresh mass)
Grain processing (bakery)	Clay, husks, dough scraps, returns	0.2 - 0.3 kg/kg Cereals
Fruit, vegetable and potato processing	Peelings and husks	0.1 - 0.35 kg/kg
Sugar manufacture	Sugar beet pulp, molasses	0.7 kg/kg sugar
Vegetable oil production	Oil press cake	1 - 3 kg/litre
Breweries	Draff, yeast	0.25 kg/litre
Wine production	Pomace	0.2 - 0.3 kg/litre
Distilleries	Distiller's wash/mash	1 - 3 kg/litre Ethanol
Dairy processing	Whey	1 - 2 kg/litre
Slaughterhouses/meat processing	Animal meal, Animal fat	15 - 60 kg/Animal

It is important to note that not all of the listed residues are used in the material sector. Many of the feedstocks listed in the table are used in the food and feed sectors, as fertilisers, or in the bioenergy and biofuel sectors.

In a few cases, some biological raw materials from the food processing sector have a PRODCOM code, so that European production figures can be found in the PRODCOM database on Eurostat's website. Eurostat is the statistical office of the European Union responsible for providing reliable and comparable data and statistics (Eurostat 2023c). In this database, however, the bio-raw materials are not explicitly classified according to their origin, but according to their use as secondary raw materials. They can be found, for instance, in the product list of the chemical class. For example, the

product "Animal fat, chemically modified" (PRODCOM code: 20.59.20.00) can be found in the chemical class (NACE class 20) of the database.

In addition, information on production volumes can be obtained from the literature. For example, the study by Grinsven et al. (2020) provides information on the production of used cooking oil from households and commercial sectors.

3.2.5.2 *Residues from other processing industries*

Other forms of biomass from the manufacturing industry included in this analysis are, for example, glycerine (PRODCOM code: 20.41.10.00) and tall oil (PRODCOM code: 20.14.71.30), both of which have respective PRODCOM codes for extracting information on production volumes. For other products of the wood industry, such as sawdust, which is produced during the sawing and cutting of wood, there is no separate PRODCOM code. Therefore, the amount of wood processed in sawmills and assumptions from the literature on the number of by-products generated have to be used to determine the total amount of residues generated. For this purpose, we use the assumptions made by Tripathi et al. (2019). In this study, waste from the initial processing of harvested wood includes branches and bark removal (about 12% of this material arrives at the mill), slabs/blocks/further chips (about 34%) and sawdust (about 12%). After kiln drying, shavings (about 6%) and sawdust/scrap (about 2%) are added to the total waste. Thus, more than 60% of by-products are generated during wood processing, of which about 15% is sawdust.

3.2.6 Wastes

In order to determine the amount of OFMSW, it is necessary to determine the total amount of waste generated by European households each year. This was done using Eurostat's Municipal Waste by Waste Management Operation database (Eurostat 2023b). In addition, according to European Compost Network (ECN) (2023), the organic fraction is: "up to 50% of municipal solid waste is organic". With this information, it was possible to approximate the organic fraction of municipal solid waste.

3.3 Trade

In order to obtain not only production figures but also trade figures for the identified biological feedstocks, the corresponding HS code was determined for each feedstock. Table 4 gives an overview of a section of biological raw materials considered and their corresponding HS-codes.

Biological Feedstock	HS-Code
Sugar Cane	170111
Sugar Beet	170112
Corn	110812
Wheat	110811
Potatoes	110813
Cassava	110814
Wheat/Cereal Straw	121300
Corn Stover	230210
Palm Oil	151110
Sunflower Oil	151211
Rapeseed Oil	151410
Soy bean oil	150700
Cotton	520100
Flax	530110
Hemp	530210
Wool (sheep)	510111
Wood (industrial)	440300
Tall Oil	380300
Sawdust	440130
Sugar Beet Pulp	230320
Brewers' spent grains	230330
Animal fat	151610
Casein (non-edible milk)	350110
Used Cooking Oil	15180095
Glycerol	152000

In addition to Comtrade, the corresponding trade figures can also be obtained from Eurostat. For this purpose, the Eurostat database "EU trade since 1988 according to HS2-4-6 and CN8 [Code: DS-045409]" is used (Eurostat 2023a). In order to obtain the desired data, a specific query has to be made to the database:

1. Product selection

The first step is to search and select the product or biological feedstock from the list using the HS code.

2. Selection of the reporter

In the context of the database, the term "reporter" refers to the Member State of the European Union that reports or provides the trade data. Eurostat collects trade data from all EU Member States and aggregates them to provide a comprehensive picture of EU trade. For this analysis, the "European Union - 27 countries" is selected in order to obtain trade data for the whole EU.

3. Choice of partners

In the context of the database, "partners" refer to the countries or regions outside the European Union with which the EU Member States trade. These are the countries or regions that trade with the EU. Eurostat collects data on trade flows between the EU and its trading partners, providing an insight into the import and export activities between the EU and the rest of the world. To get a complete picture of these trade flows, we select all 280 countries.

4. Selection of flows

"Flow" refers to the direction of trade between the European Union and its trading partners. It indicates whether the trade is imports (goods entering the EU) or exports (goods going from EU Member States to countries outside the EU). For our analysis, we select both.

5. Filtering data by time period

To obtain the most recent data, the "Years" parameter allows you to select the desired period or year. In our analysis we used the most recent years available.

Finally, the database offers the possibility of extracting the data collected and downloading them in different formats, such as tables, and inserting them into one's own data sheets. Figure 6 shows a screenshot of a query on trade data for sunflower oil via the corresponding HS code in the Eurostat database.

Figure 6: Eurostat: Example for a query to the database (screenshot; source: ...)

3.4 Biogenic Feedstocks in Material Use

The 'material use sector' in the European bioeconomy refers to the specific area within the broader bioeconomy framework that focuses on the use of renewable biological resources and biogenic feedstocks to produce materials, chemicals and products. This sector includes processes such as converting biomass into bio-based materials, replacing traditional fossil-based inputs with sustainable alternatives, and contributing to a circular economy by reducing waste and environmental impacts. An estimate or approach for the share of production and trade volumes destined for the material sector is not yet included in the analysis of biogenic feedstocks. This would be particularly important for feedstocks that are also used in the food and feed sector or in the bioenergy and biofuels sector, in order to distinguish between biogenic volumes that are used in the material sector and those that are not. However, quantifying the share of each crop used in the material sector is a major challenge. "The use of agricultural biomass for the production of biobased materials remains a major data gap." (JRC 2018; Stratmann et al. 2022) In view of Deliverable D2.4 "Report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and biobased products and materials", an attempt will be made to find ways to estimate the material use of the identified biological feedstocks.

The following table (Table 5) presents preliminary results and examples of the identified biological feedstocks and their EU domestic production and trade figures based on their HS-Codes from the analysis. Based on these results, the most suitable feedstocks will be selected according to their import relevance (highest import volume) to perform an estimation of the shares of certified and non-certified biomass flows in WP2, Task 2.2 (Matching of assessed biogenic flows with certification systems).

Table 5: Preliminary results of trade flow analysis

Feedstock Sector	Raw Biomass	European Production (Mio. t)	Production Quantity Source	Import Quantity	Export Quantity	HS-Code
Agriculture	Corn Starch	5.39	FAOSTAT	0.06	0.10	110812
Agriculture	Wheat Starch	4.09	FAOSTAT	0.01	0.09	110811
Agriculture	Cane Sugar	0.00	FAOSTAT	1.00	0.03	170111
Agriculture	Beet Sugar	15.89	FAOSTAT	0.03	0.00	170112
Agriculture	Sunflower Oil	3.59	FAOSTAT	2.23	0.89	151211
Agriculture	Palm Oil	0.00	FAOSTAT	7.11	0.15	151110
Agriculture	Wheat Straw	27.86	Own Calculation based on FAOSTAT + literature	0.08	1.67	121300
Agriculture	Cotton	0.37	FAOSTAT	0.23	0.34	
Forestry	Wood	191.89	FAOSTAT	9.53	15.90	440300
Residues (from Food processing)	Animal fat	0.80	PRODCOM	0.05	0.06	151610
Residues (from Food processing)	Sugar beet pulp	23.8	Own Calculation based on FAOSTAT + literature	1.19	0.09	230320
Residues (from paper and pulp industry)	Tall oil	0.60	PRODCOM	0.16	0.07	380300
Residues (from Biodiesel production)	Glycerol	0.69	PRODCOM	0.23	0.42	152000
Wastes	Used Cooking Oil	0.71	Literature (Grinsven et al. 2020)	1.96	0.10	15180095

5 Conclusions

The approach and methodology developed to collect volumes of biogenic feedstocks shows that a standardised approach to quantifying production and trade figures in this field is not possible. Depending on the specific type of feedstock and the related economic sector, different databases have to be consulted to obtain relevant data and information. For example, the FAOSTAT database is typically used for primary biomass and feedstocks, while the PRODCOM database is more commonly used for secondary feedstocks. For many other feedstocks, especially residues from agriculture, forestry and processing industries, data are not available in these common databases. In such cases, plausible assumptions are required for quantification, often relying on alternative data sources such as literature or findings from other research efforts. An integral aspect of the design of this methodology is the harmonisation of data from multiple databases and the use of reasonable assumptions. This combination of data and appropriate assumptions plays a key role in creating an accurate framework for assessing the quantities of different biogenic feedstocks. This combination of data and appropriate assumptions plays a key role in creating an accurate framework for assessing the volumes of different biogenic feedstocks, recognising the complexity and diversity of sources within the bioeconomy landscape.

In addition, the databases provide limited or no estimation methods to determine the proportion of biomass destined for the material sector. This distinction is particularly important for feedstocks that are also used in the food and feed sector or in bioenergy and biofuel applications. A classification that distinguishes the quantities of biogenic feedstocks used for materials from those used elsewhere in the bioeconomy would be valuable in assessing feedstock availability.

Despite these limitations, some initial conclusions can be drawn at this stage of the analysis, highlighting feedstocks that should be further examined due to their significant import volumes in the EU. Notable examples include sugar from sugar cane or oil from palm oil, both of which have high import volumes into the EU and therefore qualify as candidate feedstocks for the analysis of certified and non-certified biomass flows in the project. During the course of the project, the identified bio-based feedstocks will be further investigated on the basis of additional criteria such as availability and composition of the feedstocks. These results will play a key role e.g. in the selection of suitable value chains in Task 2.3. These selected value chains will then contribute to the forthcoming cost-benefit analysis in Work Package 5, which will be carried out later in the project.

In conclusion, the methodology for collecting volumes of biogenic feedstocks provides a basic approach for quantifying production and trade figures, even if data availability is incomplete in some cases. Based on the identified feedstocks, the STAR4BBS project aims to provide an overview of certified and non-certified biomass flows and to assess the impact and contribution of SCS and labels in the bio-based industry.

6 References

Bauchmüller, V., Carus, M., Chinthapalli, R., Dammer, L., Hark, N., Partanen, A., Ruiz, P. and Lajewski, S. 2021: BioSinn - Products for which biodegradation makes sense. nova-Institut GmbH (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, 2021-05. Download at <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/biosinn-products-for-which-biodegradation-makes-sense-pdf/>

Campuzano, R. and González-Martínez, S. 2016: Characteristics of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste and methane production: A review. *Waste Management*, Vol. 54 3-12. doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2016.05.016

Da Rosa, M. D. H., Alves, C. J., Dos Santos, F. N., De Souza, A. O., Zavareze, E. D. R., Pinto, E., Nosedá, M. D., Ramos, D. and De Pereira, C. M. P. 2023: Macroalgae and Microalgae Biomass as Feedstock for Products Applied to Bioenergy and Food Industry: A Brief Review. *Energies*, Vol. 16 (4), 1820. doi: 10.3390/en16041820

ETIP Bioenergy 2023: Starch crops for production of biofuels. (Ed.), Download at <https://www.etipbioenergy.eu/value-chains/feedstocks/agriculture/starch-crops>

European Commission 2018: A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe : strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment : updated bioeconomy strategy. Official Journal of the European Union (Ed.), 2018-10. Download at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/edace3e3-e189-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

European Compost Network (ECN) 2023: Bio-Waste in Europe. (Ed.), Download at <https://www.compostnetwork.info/policy/biowaste-in-europe/>.

European Parliament and Council 2018: Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast). Official Journal of the European Union (Ed.), 2018-12-21. Download at https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.328.01.0082.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2018:328:TOC

Eurostat 2008: NACE Rev.2 - Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community. European Parliament (Ed.), Luxembourg, Luxembourg, 2008-07. Download at <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/5902521/KS-RA-07-015-EN.PDF.pdf/dd5443f5-b886-40e4-920d-9df03590ff91?t=1414781457000>

Eurostat 2018: Economy-wide material flow accounts handbook : 2018 edition. European Commission,

Eurostat (European Parliament) 2023a: EU trade since 1988 by HS2-4-6 and CN8 [DS-045409]. Last access 2023. <http://data.europa.eu/88u/dataset/vT5w0koRS8bQHL2klzQgA>

Eurostat (European Parliament) 2023b: Municipal waste by waste management operations [ENV_WASMUN]. Last access 2023. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/view/env_wasmun?lang=en

Eurostat (European Parliament) 2023c: Sold production, exports and imports [DS-056120]. Last access 2023. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/DS-056120/legacyMultiFreq/table?lang=en>

FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO 2023: The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World (SOFI). FAO; IFAD; UNICEF; WFP; WHO; (Ed.), Rome, Italy, Download at

FAOSTAT (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) 2023a: Fisheries and Aquaculture (FishStat). Last access 2023. https://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics-query/en/aquaculture/aquaculture_quantity

FAOSTAT (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) 2023b: Crops and livestock products. Last access 2023-07-05. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>

FAOSTAT (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) 2023c: Data - Production. Last access 2023. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>

Fehrenbach, H., Giegrich, J., Köppen, S., Wern, B., Pertagnol, J., Baur, F., Huenecke, K., Dehoust, G., Bulach, W. and Wiegmann, K. 2019: BioRest: Verfügbarkeit und Nutzungsoptionen biogener Abfall- und Reststoffe im Energiesystem (Strom-, Wärme- und Verkehrssektor) Abschlussbericht (Hrsg. UBA 115/2019).

Grinsven, A., Toorn, E., van der Veen, R. and Kampman, B. 2020: Used Cooking Oil (UCO) as biofuel feedstock in the EU

Ioannidou, S. M., Pateraki, C., Ladakis, D., Papapostolou, H., Tsakona, M., Vlysidis, A., Kookos, I. K. and Koutinas, A. 2020: Sustainable production of bio-based chemicals and polymers via integrated biomass refining and bioprocessing in a circular bioeconomy context. *Bioresource Technology*, Vol. 307 123093. doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2020.123093

JRC (European Commission, Camia, A., Robert, N., Jonsson, R., Pilli, R., García-Condado, S., López-Lozano, R., Velde, M., Ronzon, T., Gurría, P., M'Barek, R., Tamosiunas, S., Fiore, G., Araujo, R., Hoepffner, N., Marelli, L. and Giuntoli, J.) 2018: Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union : first results from an integrated assessment. Publications Office (Ed.), Download at

Lewandowski, I. 2018: Bioeconomy: Shaping the Transition to a Sustainable, Biobased Economy. Springer International Publishing, Germany.

Mori Junior, R., Franks, D. M. and Ali, S. H. 2016: Sustainability certification schemes: evaluating their effectiveness and adaptability. *Corporate Governance*, Vol. 16 (3), 579-592. doi: 10.1108/CG-03-2016-0066

nova-Institut GmbH 2015: Industrial Material Use of Biomass in Europe 2015. nova-Institut GmbH (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, Download at <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/industrial-material-use-of-biomass-in-europe-2015-%E2%88%92-poster/>

nova-Institut GmbH 2022: Pathways to bio-based polymers (PNG). nova-Institut GmbH (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, 2023-02. Download at <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/pathways-to-bio-based-polymers-figure-5-png/>

nova-Institut GmbH 2023: Bio- and CO₂-based Economy nova-Institut GmbH (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, Download at

Piotrowski, S., Essel, R., Carus, M., Dammer, L. and Engel, L. 2015: Nachhaltig nutzbare Potenziale für Biokraftstoffe in Nutzungskonkurrenz zur Lebens- und Futtermittelproduktion, Bioenergie sowie zur stofflichen Nutzung in Deutschland, Europa und der Welt. nova-Institut Europa und der Welt (Ed.), Download at

Porc, O., Hark, N., Carus, M., Dr. Carrez, D. and BIC 2022: European Bioeconomy in Figures 2008–2019. Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC) (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, 2022-10. Download at <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/european-bioeconomy-in-figures-2008-2019-pdf/>

Rahikainen, M., Smason, R. and Yang, B. 2021: Global production of macroalgae and uses as food, dietary supplements and food additives. (Ed.),

Rudra, S. and Jayathilake, M. 2022: 5.08 - Hydrothermal Liquefaction of Biomass for Biofuel Production. *Comprehensive Renewable Energy (Second Edition)*. Letcher, T. M. (Ed.). Elsevier, Oxford.

Sarmento, L. 2016: Standards and Regulations for the Bio-based Industry STAR4BBI. nova-Institut GmbH (Ed.), Hürth, Germany, 2016-12.

Stratmann, M., Ugarte, S., Kähler, F. and Gulati, M. 2022: Study of the environmental sustainability requirements of bio-based value chains and supply chains for bio-based industry in future EU funded R&I demonstration and flagship projects. nova-Institut GmbH & SQ Consult B.V. (Ed.), Hürth, Germany & Bunnik, Netherlands, 2022-02.

Tripathi, N., Hills, C., Singh, R. and Atkinson, C. 2019: Biomass waste utilisation in low-carbon products: harnessing a major potential resource. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, Vol. 2 1-10. doi: 10.1038/s41612-019-0093-5

Tubiello, F., Salvatore, M., Rossi, S., Ferrara, A., Fitton, N. and Smith, P. 2013: The FAOSTAT database of greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture. *Environmental Research Letters*, Vol. 8 015009. doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/8/1/015009

UN Comtrade (United Nations) 2023: United Nations Statistics Division, UN COMTRADE. International Merchandise Trade Statistics. Last access 2023. <https://comtradeplus.un.org>

Weiss, M., Haufe, J., Carus, M., Brandão, M., Bringezu, S., Hermann, B. and Patel, M. K. 2012: A Review of the Environmental Impacts of Biobased Materials. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, Vol. 16 S169-S181. doi: 10.1111/j.1530-9290.2012.00468.x

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